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Modelling approaches for physiological evaluation and prediction of physiological responses

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Simon Annaheim, Agnes Psikuta, Patrick Eggenberger, Piero Fontana, René Rossi

Empa, Laboratory for Biomimetic Membranes and Textiles, Lerchenfeldstrasse 5, 9014 St. Gallen, Switzerland

Introduction

Physiological data has been of interest in order to provide the basis for clothing and textile developments as well as for the evaluation thereof. However, the organization and realization of human subject trials is time-consuming and expensive and ethical aspects have to be considered. In addition, inter- and intra-subject variability adds complexity to data interpretation. For this reason, mathematical models have been developed to simulate physiological responses to specific exposures including environmental conditions and clothing [1, 2]. Nevertheless, the measurement of physiological data has recently become a relevant topic as numerous tools and devices for monitoring single and multiple physiological parameters became available. These tools include activity trackers, wearable heart rate monitors or smart watches and were mainly used privately to quantify individual activity levels or monitor improvements in physical performance. Furthermore, developments in electronics and sensor technology enable their integration in smart textiles. More and more, these tools are being considered for application in occupational and clinical settings, for example, for the early detection of the deterioration of health status (e.g. heat stress or adverse responses to medication) to improve occupational safety and patient care. In order to provide the required information, physiological parameters (e.g. core body temperature) and health conditions not directly measurable need to be estimated. The aim of this presentation is to provide an overview on the activities and contributions of the Laboratory for Biomimetic Membranes and Textiles to the further development of mathematical models for physiological responses, to the evaluation of accuracy and reliability of physiological monitoring tools as well as to the development of numerical models for the estimation of physiological parameters as well as health conditions.

Models

The research interests in the field of mathematical models for physiological responses encompass two main aspects such as the accurate simulation of heat and mass transfer in clothing and the development of a database for the validation of mathematical models. The more detailed and accurate simulation of heat and mass transfer in clothing aims at improving the assessment of body-environment interactions. We follow two different approaches in our lab: one includes the development of adaptive manikins [3]; the other comprises the development of a realistic numerical clothing model simulating the most relevant heat transfer phenomena occurring in clothing systems. This includes natural and forced convection, evaporation and condensation as well as wicking of liquid moisture. In addition, air gap thickness distribution [4] as well as the effect of movement on heat transfer [5] is considered. The development of a database for the validation of mathematical models includes the thorough selection of human subject trials providing detailed information about the experimental protocol including environmental exposure and sensor application. It aims at ensuring the comparability between models as well as to define their range of application [6] and provides a valuable basis for the further development of models.

The evaluation of the accuracy and reliability of monitoring tools is done based on advanced physical models [7] as well as human subject data acquired either from controlled human subject trials conducted in our facilities [8] or in real field and clinical conditions [9]. In both cases, there is a close collaboration with clinical and industrial partners which considers the application of such monitoring solutions. The tools are compared to reference devices and the acceptability of deviations is discussed with partners.

Finally, we develop models based on statistical and machine learning approaches for the estimation of physiological parameters such as core body temperature [10] or health conditions (e.g. severity of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome) which would provide the basis for occupational safety applications as well as applications for a closer monitoring of patients in clinical as well as home settings (telemedicine).

Conclusions

The relevance and impact of developments of models for the physiological evaluation as well as for the non-invasive prediction of physiological parameters and health status highly depends on the amount and quality of data gathered as well as the appropriate application of modelling approaches. All aspects are thoroughly considered by having activities in the fields of mathematical model development, evaluation of monitoring tools as well as development of models for the estimation of physiological parameters and by having an interdisciplinary team working closely together.

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